

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
Schedule	Information (PDF)	Schedule for the workshop providing a breakdown of topics and timings	Included in this Zenodo record
Hybrid genome assembly - Nanopore and Illumina	Online tutorial (webpage)	Online tutorial on which this workshop is based. Tutorial includes slides, exercises and examples.	Available via Melbourne Bioinformatics https://www.melbournebioinformatics.org.au/tutorials/tutorials/hybrid_assembly/nanopore_assembly/